

Yields were corrected to 12% grain moisture.

Coating rice seeds with relatively small amounts of zinc resulted in increased grain yields each year. The mean increase over the 4 years was 1 t/ha, ranging from 0.6 to 1.6 t/ha (see table).

Although yield increases were significant, zinc deficiency symptoms were observed in all plots each year. But the symptoms were less severe and occurred later with zinc seed treatment. The symptoms of zinc deficiency indicate that the seed treatment, although beneficial, did not

supply all the zinc that the plants needed in the Crowley soil. Other zinc sources are being evaluated, along with higher rates of zinc seed coatings, to overcome the deficiency. □

Response of direct-seeded rice to zinc application in Sudan Gezira

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Direct-seeded rice in the Sudan Gezira often shows symptoms of zinc deficiency, particularly in early growth stages. Although most symptoms usually disappear soon after continuous flooding begins (5–6 weeks after seeding), the effect of flooding on available zinc in the soil has not been determined. Therefore, to determine the importance of zinc application to rice production (IR298-12-1-1) in the Gezira, an experiment with 5 levels of zinc (0, 2, 4, 6, and 8 kg Zn/ha) was established in 1977 at the Gezira Research Farm. The design was randomized complete block with six replications. At seeding, the zinc,

Effects of zinc level on plant height, grain yield, straw yield, and major components of grain yield of IR298-12-1-1 planted at Gezira Research Station, Sudan.

Zinc level (kg Zn/ha)	Plant ht (cm)	Grain yield (kg/ha)	Straw yield (kg/ha)	Panicles (no./m ²)	Grains (no./panicle)	1,000-grain wt (g)
0	83	4,143	6,688	398	75	20.1
2	85	4,333	7,076	387	17	20.2
4	84	4,250	6,688	396	15	20.3
6	85	4,514	7,076	417	77	20.3
8	87	4,662	7,628	398	76	20.3
S.E.	1.17	144	188	13.5	3.2	0.02

as zinc sulfate, was incorporated into the soil (heavy clay with av. pH of 8.5). The effects of zinc level on plant height, straw yield, and major grain yield components were determined.

The experiment showed that Gezira soils are slightly deficient in available zinc (see table). Grain and straw yields increased progressively with level of

applied zinc (P = 0.05). The application of 8 kg Zn/ha increased grain yield by 12% and straw yield by 14%. The increase in grain yield suggests the positive effect on dry matter production of applied zinc, which increased straw yield and grain specific weight. Zinc level had no significant effect on plant height, number of grains per panicle, or number of tillers. □

Production of blue-green algae in the field

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Blue-green algae harness solar energy to fix nitrogen. The rice plants use the nitrogen released by the blue-green algae. Thus, a rice field is an efficient nonsymbiotic nitrogen-fixing ecosystem. In submerged rice soils, biological nitrogen fixation is essentially an algal process that contributes 20 to 30 kg N/ha. Mass-scale multiplication of blue-green algae was attempted in a rice field. Soil was well prepared and levelled. The plots (10 × 2 m) were laid out. Superphosphate, lime, carbofuran, and starter culture were applied at three levels (see table).

The water level in the plots was maintained at 10 cm. Superphosphate

and lime were added and mixed well with the water. The plots were inoculated with the starter culture (*Aulosira*, *Anabaena*, *Aphanthece*, *Nostoc*). Finally, carbofuran was applied to control soil insects. The plots were not disturbed.

When daily evaporation was high, the plots were irrigated intermittently. The algae grew rapidly. In about 10 days algae formed a thick mat floating on the water surface. Fifteen days after inoculation the plots were allowed to dry

Mass production of blue-green algae in the field, Tamil Nadu, India.

Treatment	Soil-based blue-green algal yield (kg)				Mean algal yield (kg)
	Rep. 1	Rep. 2	Rep. 3	Rep. 4	
Superphosphate : 500 g Lime : 50 g Carbofuran : 100 g Starter culture : 500 g	18.7	19.4	21.2	15.2	18.6
Superphosphate : 1000 g Lime : 100 g Carbofuran : 150 g Starter culture : 1000 g	20.6	18.9	22.1	24.5	21.5
Superphosphate : 1500 g Lime : 150 g Carbofuran : 200 g Starter culture : 1500 g	24.2	25.3	24.6	22.6	24.1

in the sun. The algal flakes from the surface of the plots were collected or scraped and stored. The mean yield of algal flakes per plot was 18–24kg (see table). Differences in the algal yield with various treatment levels were small.

Studies on the cultivation of azolla in rice fields

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New technical measures combined with paired narrow rows were introduced in China in 1973 to encourage year-round cultivation of azolla with rice in paddy fields. By the paired narrow rows technique, azolla propagation could be prolonged without interfering with rice

Yield distribution of rice and azolla in a field where azolla was grown year round. Pucheng, Fukien, China.

Yields (t/ha)		Distribution (%)
<i>Rice</i>		
9.0– 10.0		3.3
10.0– 12.0		25.1
12.0– 13.5		37.4
15.0		34.0
<i>Azolla</i>		
30.0– 31.5		2.3
37.5–112.5		15.9
112.5–150		18.8
150		23.0

growth, ensuring azolla yields several times higher than those in ordinary rice culture.

The rice seedlings are transplanted in double rows. Pairs of rows are spaced 53 to 66 cm apart, with a 13.2-cm spacing between the 2 narrow rows, and a 6.6-cm spacing between hills. Azolla is

then grown in the broad space between pairs of double rows. The closer distance between wider rows (about 50 cm) is suitable for dwarf varieties.

In 1977, this technique was tested at various brigades in Pucheng, Fukien. The average yield of the rice was 6.52 t/ha per crop and the average yield of fresh azolla was 54.5 t/ha per rice crop. The distributions of rice and azolla yield are shown in the table.

In experiments using only harvested azolla as fertilizer in the field (with no added N fertilizer) 9.9 t of rice/ha was harvested from 2 crops grown at 2 sites.

Seventy-five tons of fresh azolla per hectare can supply enough nitrogen for rice yields of 7.5 t/ha.

Successful use of the technique depends on 1) proper spacing of the pairs of rows, 2) proper and sufficient nutrients for both rice and azolla, 3) good water management, and 4) pest control. □

Efficacy of some fungicides against *Trichoconis padwickii*

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The fungus *Trichoconis padwickii* has caused seedling blight, leaf spot, and grain discoloration in many released and pre-release rice varieties in several parts of Mandya, Mysore, and Mercara districts,

Karnataka, since 1976 kharif. To develop a spray schedule, the efficacy of certain fungicides in suppressing spore germination and mycelial growth of the incitant fungus was studied *in vitro*. Eight popular fungicides were tested and found to be effective in the following order: Bavistin, Benlate, Diltzane-M-45, Blitax-50, Difolatan, Hinosan-50, Brassicol, and F. M. Spray.

The systemic fungicide Bavistin was apparently superior to others at all concentrations. At 0.1% strength,

Bavistin completely inhibited spore germination and mycelial growth; Benlate, Dithane M-45, and Blitax-50 gave complete control at 0.2% strength. Hinosan-50 was not superior at 0.05% strength (the dosage usually recommended for blast control) but gave 96–97% inhibition at 0.2% strength. Difolatan, Brassicol, and F. M. Spray at 0.2% strength gave 93–97, 90–94%, and 81–93% inhibition, respectively (see table). □

Efficacy of fungicides in inhibiting the spore germination and mycelial growth of *T. pacwickii*. Kartanaka, India.

Fungicide ^a	Spore						Mycelial growth					
	Germination (%)			Inhibition (%)			Colony diameter (cm)			Inhibition (%)		
	0.05%	0.1%	0.2%	0.05%	0.1%	0.2%	0.05%	0.1%	0.2%	0.05%	0.1%	0.2%
Bavistin 50 W.P.	2.6	0.0	0.0	96.0	100.0	100.0	0.2	0.0	0.0	95	100	100
Benlate, 50 W.P	3.3	0.3	0.0	95.3	99.5	100.0	0.2	0.1	0.0	94	97	100
Dithane M-45	4.6	2.0	0.3	93.0	98.0	99.5	0.2	0.1	0.0	93	97	100
Blitax-50	8.6	3.6	0.6	88.0	95.0	98.5	0.4	0.2	0.0	88	95	100
Hinosan-50	14.0	6.3	2.3	80.0	91.0	97.0	0.9	0.3	0.1	75	91	96
Difolatan	14.3	7.0	2.0	79.5	90.0	97.0	2.2	0.9	0.3	55	82	93
Brassiccol	28.6	12.6	4.3	59.0	82.0	94.0	1.6	0.6	0.2	36	73	90
F.M. Spray	29.6	15.3	4.6	57.7	78.0	93.4	2.5	1.1	0.7	28	70	81

^a Control: spore germination recorded at 15 hours (70%) and colony diameter after 10 days of incubation (3.5 cm).